

PREDICTIVE ACOUSTICS SOFTWARE - IMPROVING STUDIO ERGONOMICS THROUGH THE CONTROL OF ROOM MODES AND ELIMINATION OF STANDING WAVES

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ABSTRACT

Studio ergonomics is concerned with how the studio is designed for maximum comfort, efficiency, safety and ease of use. Thus, the most important aspects of studio ergonomics are soundproofing (sound isolation) and sound conditioning (acoustic treatment). Their common aim is how to manage and control sound into, out of and within the studio. This is necessary because the structural parameters (i.e. the acoustics – shapes and dimensions of the room) do cause problems: either by coloring the sonic quality of recordings or distorting monitoring perception of the recording engineer. Therefore, this article is poised to shed more light on role of structural parameters in the control of room modes and the elimination of standing waves.

KEYWORD: Primary modes, axial mode frequency, standing waves, studio room dimension ratio, reverberation and structural parameters.

INTRODUCTION

According to (Roberts 2001), the most important aspects of studio ergonomics are soundproofing and acoustic treatment; thus, their common aim is how to manage and control sound into, out of and within the studio.

Note that because of reflections, both the direct sound from the monitor loudspeakers and an appreciable amount of reverberation (as the sound bounces around the room) are heard. In a good listening room, the reverb time should be too short to be perceptible under normal circumstances (White 1998a). This is because objects within the studio (including wall surfaces) do reproduce (or increase/decrease) sound waves coming from other objects (especially sources such as speakers). Moreover, different materials and structures reflect different parts of the audio spectrum more efficiently than others, so the reverb that is heard is 'coloured' – i.e. it doesn't have a flat frequency response (White 1998b). In other words, sound coloration simply means that the acoustic modes enhance certain frequencies and dull others (Science and Engineering Encyclopedia 2008).

This phenomenon of sound reflection and reproduction is known as resonance or mode. It explains how sound behaves within the studio. The room mode/resonance depends strongly on its dimension (height, length and width), which is responsible for reflections known as standing waves. Standing waves are produced when waves of equal frequency and intensity traveling in opposite directions combine. The resultant effect is the production of a stationary wave characterized by points of zero vibration and points of maximum vibration (Garba 2007).

These points of vibration form the standing wave pattern. A standing wave pattern is a vibrational pattern created within a medium when the vibrational frequency of the source causes reflected waves from one end of the medium to interfere with incident waves from the source. This interference occurs in such a manner that specific points along the medium appear to be standing still. Because the observed wave pattern is

characterized by points which appear to be standing still, the pattern is often called a standing wave pattern (Henderson 2007).

Modal coupling is a result of the interaction of the sound source and the reflective surfaces of a room. It is associated with closed specular-reflection paths (loops) whose lengths are multiples of the wavelength considered. It affects mainly those listening positions that lie within the closed paths, though diffusion may blur this effect to adjacent positions. According to how many surfaces the corresponding closed path hits, room modes are called axial, tangential and oblique. Axial modes (created along the dimensions of the room) are the easiest to calculate and to locate its corresponding nodes (where vibration is damped) (Beranek 1993). The primary "axial" mode involves reflections from two opposing surfaces. Additional resonances are created by reflections that ricochet off four different surfaces. These "tangential" resonances are generally weaker, because energy is lost at each reflection. Finally, there are "oblique" resonances which ricochet off all six surfaces (Science and Engineering Encyclopedia 2008).

Every rectangular room has three sets of primary modes, with one each for the length, width, and height. For dimensions given in feet, the first mode occurs at 1130 (the speed of sound in feet per second) divided by twice the dimension (Winer 2006). There is a simple formula for calculating the axial mode frequency of a given dimension. Lowest Mode Frequency = $1130/2 \times \text{Dimension}$ in feet. Note that the largest dimension of the room determines the lowest resonance (Science and Engineering Encyclopedia 2008). For instance, for a room with 8 feet in length, the first mode is 70.625Hz ($1130/2 \times 8$). It should be noted that each of the room dimensions (height, length and width) will encourage certain frequencies whose wavelengths are related to them. For instance, if the room is 8 feet in length, a set of axial modes at 70Hz and the harmonics of 70Hz (140Hz, 210Hz, 280Hz and so on) will be created, a second set for the room width, and yet another for its height (Walker 2006).

Reverberation is created whenever sound energy is fed into a room and the room modes are excited. When the source of energy is removed, the reverberation will decay at a rate determined by the geometry and absorbency of the room and its contents. Excessive low-frequency reverberation related to one dominating mode can cause serious problems, which could lead to over/under use of equalizer to compensate for the apparent bass boost, but then when the mix is played back on a properly balanced hi-fi system, the result sounds bass-light. Furthermore, excessive reverb time at one frequency can cause notes to hang on, generally blurring the sound and making it more difficult to concentrate on fine details (White 1998c).

For recording engineers, problems caused by standing waves and acoustic interference are often evident when their mixes are not "portable," or do not "translate" well. That is, songs that have been equalized and balanced to sound good in a particular control room do not sound the same in other rooms. Of course, variations from different loudspeakers are a factor too. But bass frequencies are the most difficult to judge when mixing because acoustic interference affects them more than higher frequencies (Winer 2006).

In a normal music listening environment, sound coming from the speakers is reflected from the walls and other surfaces in ways that can be both musically constructive and destructive. So the secret of good studio/control room design is to try to avoid the wrong type of reflections, while encouraging and controlling the right type. A well-diffused reverberation with an reverb time of around 0.3 seconds is generally considered to be about right for most rooms. Well-diffused, spectrally neutral reflections, arriving very shortly after the original sound, tend to fuse with it and increase its subjective level. However, these reflections should be at least 10dB lower in level than the direct sound for the best results, which usually means avoiding reflections that originate from surfaces close to the speakers themselves. It also means avoiding reflections from materials that only reflect a part of the audio spectrum (White 1998b).

Therefore, the standard modal approach for designing a room with good acoustics is to create as many different resonances as possible, and to spread them as evenly as possible across the frequency spectrum (Science and Engineering Encyclopedia 2008). That is why it is widely accepted that the quickest solution

to controlling room modes is via acoustic treatment – where the use of sound absorbing/diffusing materials are placed in the areas of high pressure (Winer 2006). For example, to damp a mode produced by two opposite walls, the absorbent material must be placed on one of the walls. Therefore, it is *reflections* that cause acoustic interference, standing waves, and resonances, and those are what reduce the level of low frequencies that are produced in a room. When the reflections are reduced by applying bass traps, the frequency response within the room improves (Winer 2006). However, it is more effective to put into consideration the structural parameters of the room before the studio is even constructed.

Recommended Structural Parameters

Studio structural parameters depend on the design variables. The main design variables are the room dimensions and reflection coefficients of the surfaces (walls, floor, ceiling and objects within the room), where ranges of possible room dimensions, reflection coefficients and positions of sound sources and listeners are given (Beranek 1962). However, this article is considering mainly the room dimensions.

Table 1 Studio Room Dimension Ratios

	Ratio Type 1			Ratio Type 2			Ratio Type 3		
	Height (ft)	Width (ft)	Length (ft)	Height (ft)	Width (ft)	Length (ft)	Height (ft)	Width (ft)	Length (ft)
Ratio Values	1	1.14	1.39	1	1.28	1.54	1	1.6	2.33
Small Room	10	11.4	13.9	10	12.8	15.4	10	16	23.3
	15	17.1	20.85	15	19.2	23.1	15	24	34.95
Medium Room	20	22.8	27.8	20	25.6	30.8	20	32	46.6
	30	34.2	41.7	30	38.4	46.2	30	48	69.9
	50	57	69.5	50	64	77	50	80	116.5
Large Hall/ Theatre	100	114	139	100	128	154	100	160	233
	200	228	278	200	256	308	200	320	466
	300	342	417	300	384	462	300	480	699

It is assumed that sound is originated in any of the possible sound source positions and may be received/perceived in any of the listening positions (no optimal placement of listeners or sound sources is sought after). The main goal of controlling room modes and eliminating/minimizing standing waves is to obtain a nearly flat frequency response over the range of possible source and listener positions in the studio (Queiroz 2008).

In most studios, the frequency response of the monitoring loudspeakers is expected be +/-3dB over the range 50Hz to 16kHz. This strongly depends on the structural parameters of room (even though acoustic treatment does help in this regard) (Walker 2006). Therefore, architecturally, you should avoid any form of concave structure such as a bay window or curved wall. This is because they tend to focus (gather) reflected sound into one place; the resultant effect can seriously affect the room mode when monitoring near the focal point. On the other hand, convex or irregular surfaces are generally desirable, as they help to diffuse (scatter) high frequencies leading to a more even sound field (Garba 2007).

Practically speaking, modal problems are most serious at lower frequencies and unfortunately in smaller rooms (where low frequency modes are often strong). To stand a reasonable chance of achieving good acoustics, choose room dimension whose combined modes are reasonably well spaced across the frequency range, particularly below about 300Hz (above this it's comparatively easy to deal with them using acoustic tiles) (Walker 2006).

Therefore, when designing a studio, make sure that the length, width, and height of the room are not the same or multiples of each other. It is because of this reason that rooms in form of cubes are not suitable for music production. The worst-case scenario would be an 8' x 8' x 8' (8' x 16' x 8') room. The reason is that,

such room dimensions are prone to creating continuous standing waves. Therefore, odd sizes such as 8' x 11' x 9' make better sounding rooms (Garba 2007).

In general, there are room dimensions ratios (adoptable by studio designers) developed by L. W. Sepmeyer (Winer 2006). Table 1 also shows some samples of these room dimensions, picked at random though.

Fig. 1 Optimal Studio Dimensions

Methodology

The analysis of the structural parameters is carried out using a predictive acoustics software called Room Mode Optimizer – developed by the author in September, 2007.

Room Mode Optimizer was developed using JAVA (as a programming paradigm). The fundamental algorithmic concept is based on rectangular room modes, which has three sets of primary modes, with one each for the length, width, and height. For dimensions given in feet, the first mode occurs at 1130 (the speed of sound in feet per second) divided by twice the dimension. The formula used for calculating the axial mode frequency of a given dimension is: $\text{Lowest Mode Frequency} = 1130/2 * \text{Dimension in feet}$.

Using RoomModeOptimizer

From Table 1 above, the dimensions of the sampled rooms confirmed to some prevalent accepted ratios. It is clear therefore, that the goal is to have a room that spreads the modes evenly throughout the low frequency range. This is only achievable by designing the room with dimensions whose length, width and height are as unrelated as possible – so that the resonances occurring concurrently would be minimized.

This is where RoomModeOptimizer comes in handy. It indicates at what frequencies the modes occur and how close together they are (Garba 2007).

For instance, use RoomModeOptimizer to find out if a studio with these dimensions (height =150ft; width = 240ft; = length 350 ft) will confirm to some of the recommended ratios. See the results from the screenshot of Fig. 1. The results indicate that resonances are evenly spread out within the room.

However, if equal dimensions or their multiples (for instance, 100x200x300ft) are inputted, the modes will occur concurrently several times within the room. That is why designing this type of studio is highly discouraged. See the screenshot of Fig. 2.

Fig. 2 Non Standard Studio Dimensions

CONCLUSION

Finally, from the above screenshots (Fig. 1 and 2), it can be deduced that one of the most important properties of a room is its *modes*, or natural resonant frequencies which are related to its length, width, and height. Generally speaking, larger rooms are better acoustically than smaller rooms because the modes are spaced more closely, yielding an overall flatter response. It is therefore, a minimum volume of at least 2,500 cubic feet is recommended for any room in which high quality music reproduction is intended (Winer 2006). In the light of the above premise, these sets of studio room dimensions (height x width x length) in feet are considered reasonable starting points: 10 x 14 x 19; 11 x 13.86 x 17.49; 11 x 14.08 x 16.94 and 12 x 13.68 x 16.68. These optimum room ratios have been suggested to minimize coloration; thus, guaranteeing a flat frequency response within the studio.

REFERENCES

- Beranek, Leo L. (1962): Music, Acoustics, and Architecture, John Wiley and Sons, New York.
- Beranek, Leo L. (1993): Acoustics, Acoustical Society of America, New York.
- Garba, E. J. (2007): Digital Audio Production & Music Technology (An introductory guide), Audiophilia Records, Nigeria.
- Henderson, Tom (2007): Standing Waves (The Physics Classroom Tutorial), Glenbrook South High School in Glenview, Illinois. <http://www.glenbrook.k12.il.us/GBSSCI/PHYS/Class/waves/u1014b.html> (accessed January 18, 2008).
- Queiroz, Marcelo (2008): Some Optimization Models for Listening Room Design, Institute of Mathematics and Statistics, University of Sao Paulo, Brazil. http://gsd.ime.usp.br/sbcm/2003/papers/dMarcelo_Queiroz.pdf (accessed January 28, 2006)
- Roberts, J. (2001): An Introduction to Recording Studio Design, AhISee.com, <http://www.ahisee.com/content/rsdpart1.html> (accessed February 19, 2006)

Science and Engineering Encyclopedia, Room Modes,
<http://www.diracdelta.co.uk/science/source/h/o/home/source.html> (accessed January 18, 2008).

Walker, Martin (2006): Optimising Your Studio Acoustics with PC Utilities, Sound on Sound, Media House, Trafalgar Way, Bar Hill, Cambridge, CB23 8SQ, United Kingdom.
http://www.soundonsound.com/sos/nov06/articles/pcmusician_1106.htm (accessed July 18, 2007)

White, Paul (1998a): Room for Improvement - Practical Acoustic Treatment: Part 1, Sound on Sound, Media House, Trafalgar Way, Bar Hill, Cambridge, CB23 8SQ, United Kingdom.
<http://www.soundonsound.com/sos/jul98/articles/acoustics1.html> (accessed January 28, 2006)

White, Paul (1998b): Room for Improvement - Practical Acoustic Treatment: Part 3, Sound on Sound, Media House, Trafalgar Way, Bar Hill, Cambridge, CB23 8SQ, United Kingdom.
http://www.soundonsound.com/sos/sep98/articles/acoustic_3.html (accessed January 28, 2006)

White, Paul (1998c): Room for Improvement - Practical Acoustic Treatment: Part 4, Sound on Sound, Media House, Trafalgar Way, Bar Hill, Cambridge, CB23 8SQ, United Kingdom.
<http://www.soundonsound.com/sos/oct98/articles/acoustics.html> (accessed January 28, 2006)

Winer, Ethan (2006): Acoustic Treatment and Design for Recording Studios and Listening Rooms, Ethan Winer and RealTraps, LLC, USA. <http://www.ethanwiner.com/acoustics.html> (accessed February 19, 2006)

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